

SOME NOTIONS ON LEAST COMMON MULTIPLES

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In [1] Smarandache LCM Sequence has been defined as $T_n = \text{LCM} (1 \text{ to } n) =$
LCM of all the natural numbers up to n.

The SLS is

1, 2, 6, 60, 420, 840, 2520, 2520, . . .

We denote the LCM of a set of numbers a, b, c, d, etc. as $\text{LCM}(a,b,c,d)$

We have the well known result that $n!$ divides the product of any set of n consecutive numbers. Using this idea we define **Smarandache LCM Ratio Sequence** of the r^{th} kind as **SLRS(r)**

The n^{th} term ${}_rT_n = \text{LCM} (n , n+1 , n+2 , \dots , n+r-1) / \text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3 , 4 , \dots , r)$

As per our definition we get SLRS(1) as

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, . . . ${}_1T_n (= n)$

we get SLRS(2) as

1, 3, 6, 10, . . . ${}_2T_n = n(n+1)/2$ (triangular numbers).

we get SLRS(3) as

$\text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3) / \text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3) , \text{LCM} (2 , 3 , 4) / \text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3) , \text{LCM} (3 , 4 , 5) /$
 $\text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3)$

$\text{LCM} (4 , 5 , 6) / \text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3) \text{LCM} (5 , 6 , 7) / \text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3)$

$\equiv 1 , 2 , 10 , 10 , 35 \dots$ similarly we have

SLRS(4) $\equiv 1 , 5 , 5 , 35 , 70 , 42 , 210 , \dots$

It can be noticed that for $r > 2$ the terms do not follow any visible patterns.

OPEN PROBLEM : To explore for patterns/ find reduction formulæ for ${}_rT_n$.

Definition: Like nC_r , the combination of r out of n given objects , We define a new term nL_r

As

${}^nL_r = \text{LCM} (n , n-1 , n-2 , \dots , n-r+1) / \text{LCM} (1 , 2 , 3 , \dots , r)$

(Numerator is the LCM of n , n-1 , n-2, . . . n-r+1 and the denominator is the LCM of first natural numbers.)

we get ${}^1L_0 = 1, {}^1L_1 = 1, {}^2L_0 = 1, {}^2L_1 = 2, {}^2L_2 = 2$ etc. define ${}^0L_0 = 1$

we get the following triangle:

1

1, 1

1, 2, 1

1, 3, 3, 1

1, 4, 6, 2, 1

1, 5, 10,, 10 5, 1

1, 6, 15, 10, 5, 1, 1

1, 7, 21, 35, 35, 7, 7, 1

1, 8, 28, 28, 70, 14, 14, 2, 1

1, 9, 36, 84, 42, 42, 42, 6, 3, 1

1, 10, 45, 60, 210, 42, 42, 6, 3, 1, 1

Let this triangle be called **Smarandache AMAR LCM Triangle**

Note: As $r!$ divides the product of r consecutive integers so does the LCM $(1, 2, 3, \dots, r)$ divide the LCM of any r consecutive numbers Hence we get only integers as the members of the above triangle.

Following properties of **Smarandache AMAR LCM Triangle** are noticable.

1. The first column and the leading diagonal elements are all unity.
2. The k^{th} column is nothing but the SLRS(k).
3. The first four rows are the same as that of the Pascal's Triangle.
4. II^{nd} column contains natural numbers.
5. III^{rd} column elements are the triangular numbers.
6. If p is a prime then p divides all the terms of the p^{th} row except the first and the last which are unity. In other words $\sum p^{\text{th}} \text{ row} \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$

Some keen observation opens up vistas of challenging problems:

In the 9^{th} row 42 appears at three consecutive places.

OPEN PROBLEM:

(1) Can there be arbitrarily large lengths of equal values appear in a row.?

2. To find the sum of a row.
3. Explore for congruence properties for composite n .

SMARANDACHE LCM FUNCTION:

The Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as $S(n) = k$ where k is the smallest integer such that n divides $k!$. Here we define another function as follows:

Smarandache Lcm Function denoted by $S_L(n) = k$, where k is the smallest integer such that n divide LCM $(1, 2, 3, \dots, k)$.

Let $n = p_1^{a_1} p_2^{a_2} p_3^{a_3} \dots p_r^{a_r}$

Let p_m^{am} be the largest divisor of n with only one prime factor, then

We have $S_L(n) = p_m^{\text{am}}$

If $n = k!$ then $S(n) = k$ and $S_L(n) > k$

If n is a prime then we have $S_L(n) = S(n) = n$

Clearly $S_L(n) \geq S(n)$ the equality holding good for n a prime or $n = 4, n = 12$.

Also $S_L(n) = n$ if n is a prime power. ($n = p^a$)

OPEN PROBLEMS:

- (1) Are there numbers $n > 12$ for which $S_L(n) = S(n)$.
- (2) Are there numbers n for which $S_L(n) = S(n) \neq n$

REFERENCE:

- [1] Amarnath Murthy, Some new smarandache type sequences, partitions and set, SNJ, VOL 1-2-3, 2000.